

INTEGRATION OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6548182>

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The skillful aim of teaching a foreign language as of late is the construction then actualization about a "secondary linguistic personality" of a student so a person's ability after absorb a complete part among intercultural communication, i.e. successfully elevate out convivial interplay along carriers about a exclusive tradition [11, p. 65]. In kilter in accordance with improve a less linguistic personality, an unaccompanied desire have according to grasp the verbal-semantic articles concerning any other call (the linguistic image regarding the world about partial speakers), as properly so the "global (conceptual) picture about the world" [11, p. 68]. The made "secondary linguistic personality" implies the capacity according to successfully uses the FL into a range of fields over activity, incl. professional, as nicely as the capacity because of self-development among the language, academic then socio-cultural environments. The process of form concerning a secondary linguistic personality is immediately influenced by way of the conventional approaches arrival vicinity in the world.

Modern tribe society is highly dynamic, and one of the just necessary tasks on the teacher is a timely answer to them. Already today, of the stipulations of the statistics society, the professionalism over a specialist among some discipline is determined no longer only via the quantity on knowledge, but additionally by using the ability in conformity with independently find the quintessential information, navigate information flows, quickly highlighting the integral statistics then ignoring others, while efficaciously the usage of the contemporary technologies. Moreover, nowadays a tremendous section over communication, incl. intercultural, conveyed out remotely the usage of digital technologies. These tendencies determine recent procedures then strategies on teaching a foreign language.

To advance a “secondary language personality” today, standard counsel methods are no longer enough. We need recent techniques up to expectation would enable school students in conformity with boost the imperative knowledge, knowledge then expertise for the profitable implementation on communication, expert yet instructional things to do in the modern high-tech information-saturated ball [12, p. 17]. On the groundwork about the well-acquainted literature, we cease that it aim will be done by integrating present day multimedia or digital applied sciences within the manner over discipline a foreign (English) language, as perform be effectively aged of classes meanwhile into high school.

The secondary school is a resolution stage in the learning system. Today, solely secondary (basic general) lesson (1-9 grades concerning school) is compulsory of Kazakhstan, which capability so much such covers the widest feasible category concerning citizens. Thus, the knowledge, abilities, competencies and talents acquired between less faculty structure the degree about usual discipline within the country. The intention on the petty school is in imitation of supply the most passionate and versatile education, in imitation of enhance whole the indispensable abilities so much would give the individual the probability in conformity with correctly elevate out expert things to do into the future. Such competencies include, of particular, the ability in conformity with communicate in English, as like the speech about global communication, using cutting-edge applied sciences within an information-saturated surroundings [13, p. 5].

For it reasons, within our opinion, such is extraordinarily important in imitation of begin making ready for professional life between the information class already within school.

The improvement regarding information technology has supplied a new, unique probability because of conducting classes - the introduction on range learning. It, firstly, approves the learner to pick out each the era or area because of learning, secondly, that makes that viable because of humans whosoever are deprived on arrival usual education because one motive then some other to reach an education, thirdly, after use latter data technologies into teaching, fourthly, according to a certain sum reduces the price of training. On the lousy hand, range study enhances the possibilities because of individualization on education [14, p. 39].

As a rule, digital textbooks are chronic between scale learning. The blessings over these textbooks are: firstly, their mobility, secondly, the appearance regarding conversation including the development over pc networks, yet thirdly, the adequacy of the stage of development

concerning cutting-edge scientific knowledge. On the other hand, the creation regarding electronic textbooks also contributes in conformity with solving certain a hassle as the regular updating concerning data material. They may also comprise a great number over workout routines yet examples, illustrated within detail in the dynamics of a range of types concerning information. In addition, with the assist concerning digital textbooks, advantage limit is led oversea - pc testing.

A multimedia laptop is no longer only an instant integrated storage medium, such is a device so nearly entirely yet appropriately displays the "face à face" model. In addition, statistics yet allusion structures based totally regarding hypermedia links do keep applied only between computers, who are additionally one of the nearly essential aspects about the individualization regarding discipline [15, p.68].

Typically, a multimedia textbook is a employ over teaching, controlling, modeling then mean packages positioned concerning magnetic media, who reflect the most important scientific content material over the tutorial discipline. A multimedia textbook fast complements a everyday one, and is specially high-quality now it:

- gives almost on the spot feedback;
- helps according to shortly find the vital records (including apposite search), which is hard in imitation of discover among a normal textbook;
- Significantly saves period together with a couple of references to hypertext explanations;
- along together with a quick textual content - shows, tells, models, etc. (this is the place the chances then blessings over multimedia applied sciences appear) lets in you in conformity with quickly, but at the move close appropriate for a particular individual, take a look at potential into a particular piece [16, p. 16].

Hypertext and hypermedia tools.

Hypertext is a method concerning non-linear present regarding textual material, into which the text consists of phrases highlighted of incomplete road to that amount are composite in accordance with certain textual content fragments. Thus, the person does no longer just scroll thru the pages of text in order, he can deviate beside the linear account by means of some link, i.e. she manages the system concerning issuing information. In a hypermedia system, snap shots do lie aged namely fragments, or facts perform include text, graphics, video clips, and sound.

The use on hypertext science satisfies certain requirements because of textbooks as much structuredness, amenities about use. If necessary, such a textbook be able be "laid out" on any server then such may lie without problems corrected. But, as a rule, those are characterized by using poor design, layout, structure, etc.

Currently, so are many one of a kind hypertext formats (HTML, DHTML, PHP, etc.)

Electronic dictionaries

An electronic dictionary is secure systematized lexical facts (dictionary database) saved within pc memory, as like nicely as a employ of programs because processing this facts and providing such over the screen. The electronic dictionary combines the capabilities about looking for facts about interest, demonstrating speech patterns or makes such feasible in imitation of master instructional cloth the use of a special law regarding exercises. All present day digital dictionaries use the sound capability about multimedia non-public computers according to imitate pronunciation. At present, the uses on modern-day multimedia applied sciences is positive at all ranges on discourse a foreign language or then cause including students over exceptional groups. Moreover, the range concerning technologies in discipline allows thou in imitation of edit the instructions extra intense then interesting. This strategy motivates school students to work, helps the perception regarding a foreign language. For example, now assignment along hypertext, students slave not just volume via the pages about textual content between order, it may deviate from the linear representation by any link, i.e. that manages the system regarding issuing records [17, p. 101].

Interactive board

According in accordance with the author, the uses regarding projection science within aggregate including audio capacity makes it feasible after uses abstracts, tables, movies and notice substances among the study room when explaining current material, or when examining texts, diagrams then information out of electronic dictionaries. This allows ye in accordance with put in force the principles about visibility, accessibility yet systematic present concerning the material.

However, such possibilities into the appearance about a nugget on computer- projector-screen are applied only into the viewing mode. To test written assignments and within the evaluation on the text, one has in conformity with flip once more according to everyday brush or marker boards. Here, the teacher repeatedly encounters objective difficulties: fast

an audience together with a multimedia projector can only stand outfitted along a honor yet a marker wood over pinnacle about as the dignity is installed. Thus, the at a time uses regarding each the dado and the honor becomes tough [18, p. 3].

In the affection over the above, a simply progressive creation is the SMART Board interactive whiteboard. By the usage of the whiteboard, the teacher can combine the confirmed methods and methods on a regular whiteboard with a thoroughness concerning interactive yet multimedia features.

The SMART electronic dado permits to:

1. Active commenting about the material: highlighting, clarifying, adding additional data the usage of electronic markers with the potential in conformity with trade the colour and row thickness;

2. Full-fledged assignment concerning the transport over the text then single sentences, indicating the hyperlinks then relationships between words;

3. Typing by means of skill on the virtual keyboard about anybody textual content regarding the project into anybody software yet its demonstration into actual time;

4. Not solely familiarity together with check duties within viewing mode, but additionally accomplishment testing concerning an singular pupil and a crew on school students because of the entire audience, condition the school does now not bear a computer classification and such can't lie furnished in imitation of the teacher at the moment;

5. Saving the consequences within a solve file for consideration as photos yet into HTML or PDF format.

Thus, using an interactive whiteboard, a permanent employment about a pupil within electronic structure can lie organized. This considerably saves time, stimulates the development concerning intellectual and innovative activity, and consists of whole school students within the classification of the work. In addition, SMART software lets in no longer only, so in the meantime mentioned, in accordance with store screen slides, but also to organize to them within the favored sequence, along with in the shape on albums [19].

The current SES of RK (State Educational Standard) on primary average study belongs according to the 2d era of certain requirements then is designed to assure the transition in conformity with a qualitatively recent mannequin on education, into who the central assignment is the improvement over the creative knowledge over students, their training for

life among modern prerequisites based totally of a system-activity approach. Thus, there is a slow change of academic paradigms: from a model shaped concerning the precept on transferring (“broadcasting”) talents out of a teacher in imitation of students, in conformity with a student-oriented one, involving the active interaction regarding entire participants of the instructional process. Moreover, SES acknowledges namely education outcomes not just the capabilities yet knowledge obtained with the aid of students of sure areas, however the knowledge that he ought to master. The competence-based approach, which types the foundation of the Bologna Declaration, is based concerning knowledge, however is accomplished between trip yet the potential according to mission instruction conditions within actual ones [20].

The answer necessities because of the SES are:

- 1) the structure about a persona prepared because self-development yet continuous education;
- 2) graph then building of the communal surroundings because of the development concerning students between the lesson system;
- 3) lively instructional yet cognitional activity on students;
- 4) arrival into estimate within the process over planning educational activities the odd age, psychological and physiological traits about school students [20].

In addition, that seems to us extraordinarily essential the want about the SES about the formation of ICT potential among the manner regarding discourse foreign languages, within vile words, over “the structure yet development regarding competence of the use on statistics yet verbal exchange technologies <...> then the improvement over inspiration after grasp the lifestyle of lively makes use of regarding dictionaries yet vile ask systems” [20].

This requirement meets the developments on contemporary society, the place the communication system is an increasing number of shifting from the actual (offline) in accordance with the virtual world (online), yet its effectiveness directly relies upon on the dimensions concerning dominion about modern-day technical capability via the contributors within the process.

Thus, today within the lesson rule at that place is a putting for informatization concerning the instruction process, fixed by a quantity concerning government initiatives.

In addition, cutting-edge traits between the developments of class are mirrored of the necessities placed on after school graduates. In today’s

high-tech and information-saturated world, the capacity yet permission after utilizes digital technologies will become an vital aspect over a person's ordinary professional competence. Therefore, between our opinion, the method over constructing a unimportant linguistic personality into petty school, as much a resolution tribune on education, must stand carried abroad the use of contemporary multimedia then digital technologies.

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№ 604. Зарегистрирован в Министерстве юстиции Республики
Казахстан 1 ноября 2018 года № 17669.
<https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V1800017669>